

THE POSITIVE SOCIO-ECONOMIC IMPACT OF SOLIDARITY ECONOMY IN RURAL WOMEN: A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF TUNISIA, AFRICA AND GLOBAL WORLD

DORSAF MAAYOUFI

PhD Scholar (Business Management), Hungarian University of agriculture and life science (Mate).
Email: Maayoufidorsaf5@gmail.com

Dr. TIBOR FARKAS

PhD Scholar, Associate professor, Hungarian University of agriculture and life science (Mate).
farkas.tibor.kumacs@gmail.com

Dr. EMESE BRUDER

PhD Scholar, Associate professor, Hungarian University of agriculture and life science (Mate).
Bruder.Emese@uni-mate.hu

Abstract:

Solidarity economy (SE) is shaping the modern ways of economics with a better involvement of the workers and hirers working together in a close liaison. The core idea of SE started with the revolutionary acts taken against the rigid implementations of neoliberal capitalism or neoliberalism which focused more on the economy itself rather than the people involved in the economical setups. The financial crisis of 2008 worked as a driving force for the development of a new strategic plan for economic development, due to the fact that neoliberalism was believed to be the cause of this crisis. Onwards from then, many countries adopted the phenomenon of an economical system which lays its foundations on a more solidarity-based approach where the lower class can feel important. The alternate movements started in France and Latin America are now adopted and practices in many civilized economies. This paper focused on understanding the current conditions of SE in context of women living in rural areas. Based on a through literature analysis, the status of SE prevailing in the world, SE in Africa and SE in Tunisia were the key targeted areas of interest.

Keywords: Solidarity economy, Social and solidarity economy, rural women, African women, Tunisian women

INTRODUCTION

Long has community development strived to alleviate persistent poverty, social inequality, and environmental problems? These issues are all linked to capitalism production and trading relations. However, capital mobility and corporate consolidation appear to limit the options for local action, as cities and regions come to be regarded as unavoidably vying with one another in a global market for limited resources, employment, and capital investment (Holland et al., 2007). With these circumstances, a discursive space has opened up from which new aspirations, opportunities, and practices for more democratic and revolutionary community development are arising; solidarity economy is one among them. The attainment of societal goals with the help of numerous economic activities involving personals from diverse backgrounds to work together as mutual. It prioritizes social profitability instead of purely financial goals. The notion

of solidarity economy suggests alternative modes of production and employment that priorities human well-being over economic maximization. The term "solidarity economy" refers to organizations such as cooperatives, associations, or mutual credit groups that are distinguished by shared ownership of the means of production and democratic administration. Their overarching goal is to offer employment and encourage empowerment via participation (Poirier, 2014). Its arousal took place from the desire to provide jobs and good living circumstances to individuals on the periphery of the capitalist economy. The notion is based in the European industrial revolution's worker's movements, when labour cooperatives sprung up to combat exploitation and unemployment (Laville, 2015).

Solidarity economy is now treated as a global phenomenon due the widespread of its roots in many nations. This concept has effected various countries from local to global levels by targeting keen variables such as microfinance and social currencies, a fair trading environment and proximity services (Laville, 2010). Tunisian market is amongst those markets which had been influenced by the new ideology of solidarity economy. However, The SE has a relatively low economic weight; it accounts for only 0.6 percent of the employed labour force and, at most, 1% of GDP (Mouelhi, Braham, & Ghazali, 2021). Agricultural activities are relatively common in the SSE, thanks to the GDAP and SMSA. The job creation dynamic is quite weak, with the bulk of solidarity institutions employing less than ten individuals, primarily volunteers (El Hidhri, 2017). Regardless of the fact that in Tunisia, SE is scattered, poorly planned and was distinguished by the presence of several actors and the absence of a coherent and organized institution presenting a shared vision for the SE as a whole, a report by Haddar, (2017) stated that despite its present small scale, solidarity economy had the potential to be a driver of long-term employment creation, particularly for young people and women in rural or disadvantaged regions of Tunisia. For this very reason, this study was aimed to analyze the situation of solidarity economy in rural Tunisia (especially among women) and compare the current status of SE with Africa and the rest of the world.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Current research used a peer reviewed search strategy of the available academic work on different platforms including Google Scholar, Science Direct, EBSCO and ProQuest. A mix of keywords such as "Solidarity economy and rural women", "Solidarity economy", "Solidarity economy and developing countries", "Solidarity economy in Africa" and "Solidarity economy in Tunisia" were used to identify papers based on the topic. In addition to this, materials from unpublished academic thesis, newspaper stories, websites, and other sources was also searched and reviewed to present an overview of the condition of solidarity economy.

After going through all the literature based on the search strategy and nature of this article, we divided this review in 3 parts. The first part of the research provided an overview of solidarity economy on a global scale, the second part streamlined the context of solidarity economy in African continent while the third part linked and compared the first two parts with the status of solidarity economy in Tunisia (especially in rural Tunisia).

THE CONCEPT OF SOLIDARITY ECONOMY AND ITS ADAPTATION IN MODERN WORLD

In the 19th century, a concept known as neoliberal capitalism or neoliberalism started to establish around the globe. This concept was associated with the idea of free market capitalism and was an important contributor to the establishment of conservative and libertarian groups, political parties, and think tanks who were responsible for the main theme of neoliberal capitalism connected with economic liberalization policies such as privatization, deregulation, globalization, free trade, austerity, and budget cuts in order to strengthen the influence of the private sector in the economy and society (Boas & Gans-Morse, 2009; HAAS, 2012). However in 2008, a financial crisis erupted with startling rapidity, as the value of mortgage-related assets that had spread throughout the US and worldwide financial systems abruptly crashed. This crisis affected several of the world's top financial institutions, causing significant harm to a huge portion of the global financial system (Nelson & Katzenstein, 2014). The financialization, or the development of huge fictitious financial riches, that began in the 1980s and the triumph of a conservative ideology, namely, neoliberalism—based on self-regulated and efficient markets, were believed to be the main causes of this crisis (Bresser-Pereira, 2010). The economic relationships that have emerged in capitalist nations over the last three decades are now being questioned on a far larger scale. This can be observed in the growing number of alternative social projects – in both the 'North' and the 'South' – that seek to rethink current market connections, particularly in creating exchange value and allowing trade access (Lee et al., 2004). These experiences are an implicit denouncement of the strictly economic approach to trade, which considers goods prices to be simply the result of competition (often unfair) between national economies, the result of which is the progressive marginalization of poorer economies, with working and living conditions being pressed downwards in the process of readjustment. Critics object to an economy that, rather than being based solely on exchange value, considers a variety of non-economic considerations in determining pricing (Navarro, 2007; Simpson, Lumsden, & McDowall Clark, 2015).

Since the mid-1980s, economic policies that have liberalized and deregulated markets for products, labour, and capital have resulted in a degradation of wage-labor connections, diminishing job security and making it more difficult for a growing proportion of the population to get monetary resources. Community money systems have been established as alternatives to traditional arrangements to prevent exclusion and support the dynamics of local development (Leyshon, Lee, & Williams, 2003; Mayo & Boyle, 1999; North, 2007). These systems were complex and unique based on the country they were forged-in yet, they had common goals; supporting territorial socioeconomic and political dynamics, establishing new economic practices based on new norms, and fostering empowerment. The LETS in Canada and the United Kingdom, time banks in Italy and the United Kingdom, barter clubs in Argentina, the Ithaca Hour in the United States, WIR-type systems in Switzerland, and the Accorderies in Quebec and France are among the few well-known examples of community money systems. These alternative experiments were consistent with thought that had been criticizing neoliberalism's flaws since the 1980s. Based on their criticism of the actual initiatives in concern, these countries suggested a new view of the economy. For instance,

'Solidarity economy'(SE); researchers who identified these tendencies advocate for more solidarity and social justice in economic connections, as well as new kinds of transaction that are more respectful of ties between people and the rest of nature (Museus, 2020). The solidarity economy emphasises collaboration, common sharing, and action, while placing the human being at the heart of economic and social progress.

The alternative movements first appeared in France and Latin America three decades ago, advocating a "social and solidarity economy" (SSE) and a "popular economy" (economy popular); nowadays, they are still thriving and have expanded to all continents under various names. Those created in English-speaking nations during the inaugural World Social Forum in Porto Alegre in 2001, particularly in the United Kingdom and the United States, are known as 'the human economy' and 'the solidarity economy,' respectively. Similar movements emerged in Africa and Asia (Allard & Davidson, 2008; Baron, 2007). In 2007, the South Korean government built a supportive legal framework and supporting institutions with the goal of creating a suitable climate for SE to emerge and grow, and as a result, a wide spectrum of organizations and enterprises based on SE had swiftly emerged in the nation since then. From 55 in 2007 to 1825 in 2017, the number of organizations and enterprises had grown (Korean labor institute, 2018). The same report believed that these organizations and enterprises in South Korea had a 78.1 % contribution to employment generation. Female labour force participation rate in South Korea had an average value of 49.74 percent in between 1993-2019, with a low of 46.87 percent in 1993 and a high of 53.77 percent in 2019 (The World Bank, 2019). If the non-profit or third-sector figures are used as a starting point, an average of 5 to 10% of the working population is observed in many nations. According to another report; Sweden, Belgium, France, Holland, and Italy had between 9 and 11.5% of their working population engaging in some form of SSE enterprises. The number of workers in SE firms were found to be risen over the previous decade, from 11 million in 2002-2003 to 15 million in 2016, accounting for 6.5% of the EU's working population (Nardi, 2016). All of these countries had a fair share of women labor who added up to the workforce both on rural and urban fronts. Further, Dubois (2021) examined the impact of SE implicated by SE centers, on poverty in Brazil. Beneficiaries highlighted improvements in basic material requirements, improved market inclusion, and socio-political empowerment. The data suggested that the centers based on SE interacted with these three conceptualizations. Members increased their fundamental material needs, reducing poverty as a result of a lack of money. They acquired access to economic occupations and product marketplaces, so resolving poverty as exclusion. Participants gained socio-political empowerment through conscientization and education, as evidenced by female emancipation and environmental consciousness, with poverty as a source of power imbalance. Small changes in living conditions make a big effect for SEE members. For rural female respondents, working in a solidarity economy group was the first time they had an occupation outside of their family and were able to make autonomous decisions, generating an income apart from their spouses. In rural communities, women frequently marry young to leave their parent home and raise a family, while males shoulder the financial burden of maintaining the household. The SEEs provided them with a different vocational viewpoint as well as the possibility to take on leadership responsibilities. Through SEE, they occupied

leading positions and gained access even to male dominated fields (Dubois, 2021). Moreover, the impact of SE on labour inclusion of people with disabilities in Spain showed that in comparison to capitalist companies, SE had a better contribution in achieving sustainable global development goal of providing equal wages to the labor. They favor work and its quality for individuals with disabilities to a higher extent (Calderón-Milán, Calderón-Milán, & Barba-Sánchez, 2020). Another example of SE is MGNREGA program from India enacted in 2005. Initially, this programme provided 100 days (which were gradually increased) of guaranteed pay work in each fiscal year (April-March) for all enrolled unskilled job seekers (both women and men). The MGNREGA included enabling measures for women, with the goal of ensuring that at least 33% of participating employees were women, as well as equal pay for men and women. There were additional provisions for services such as daycare at work locations to remove obstacles to women's labour participation. Further, this programme focused on the need that work be supplied within 5 kilometres of the worker's house in order to allow more women to work under this programme. In rural India, where manual casual labour was the primary source of income for majority of households, a job "guarantee" programme like the MNREGA based on Social Justice for a Fair Globalization provided better opportunities for solidarity based work (Dash & Morais, 2015). With this discussion it can be made clear that SE is providing a baseline of equality for labors especially female labors belonging to backward rural areas, with the ideology of solidarity in workplace which is helping achieve the goals as well as making the labor comfortable.

SOLIDARITY ECONOMY IN AFRICA

At the time when SE was being invented and adopted in many regions of the world, its effects started to flourish making entry in new countries. The global financial crisis had a wide-ranging influence on African economies. The most notable were the decreases in export pricing and volumes. Many nations have seen dramatic decreases in basic commodity exports, owing mostly to declining commodity prices and demand. Non-energy commodity prices fell 38% in the second half of 2008. Between July and December 2008, oil prices plunged by 69% (Ali, 2009). This situation demanded a more effective framework to deal with the situation which came in the form of a conference inaugurated by the international labor organization. This conference was attended by nearly 200 African social economy promoters and stakeholders, government representatives from 25 African nations, employers' and workers' groups, SE organizations from other parts of the globe, and ILO headquarters units and field specialists. They agreed on a Plan of Action to mobilize the SSE in Africa in response to the crisis at the local, national, and regional levels (International labor organizations, 2009). The ILO's International Training Centre (ITC) sponsored the first Interregional Academy on Social and Solidarity Economy in 2010, which was a critical step toward achieving global agreement on the core characteristics and universal principles of the SSE and its organizations and companies in Africa. This academy helped in the understanding and implementation of SE among the African society. Participants of the academy worked and helped others understand about the necessity for the SSE to be recognized globally as a niche between the public and private sectors (Fonteneau et al., 2011).

In many parts of the world including Africa, Non-Profit organizations (NPO) have their roots to promote social welfare and overall wellbeing of the society. Most of the time these organizations are dependent on funding yet the lack of such resources can make them prone to diminish. To survive, these organizations are increasingly transforming into "non-profit enterprises" or "social businesses," as they can no longer rely on external or donor funding (Watson, 2019). Because a lack of financing has an influence on sustainability, South African non-profits are increasingly forced to earn their own money by selling services and/or commodities which is promoting the ideology of SE. The total number of registered NPO in South Africa is 254,571 in 2021 (Department of Social Development, 2015). The NPO in South Africa was dominated by black women who lead and administered it. 59% of management jobs were held by women while 60% of the full-time employees were women (S. J. I. T. C. Steinman, ILO. Retrieved December, 2017). Social enterprises are also the key for the establishment of SE (Fraisie, Gardin, Laville, Petrella, & Richez-Battesti, 2016), its major goal is to address social issues using a financially sustainable business model in which surpluses (if any) are mostly reinvested for the stated purpose (S. Steinman, 2010). With growing hope about their ability to bridge gaps in health coverage, contribute to sustainable development objectives, and reach out to developing nations' most remote and neglected areas (Schaaf et al., 2018). The majority of community health workers in Africa are women who work under health social enterprise. BRAC Africa, a non-governmental organization, has educated over 6000 CHWs in Uganda, Liberia, Sierra Leone, and South Sudan to deliver medical care through house visits, with CHWs earning money by selling over-the-counter drugs and other health goods (Björkman Nyqvist, Guariso, Svensson, & Yanagizawa-Drott, 2019). These social enterprise activities are not only helping the community women to earn for living but also provide the means for sustainable global development. Cooperative societies are also an important element of SE. Nigeria, a country in West Africa showed great improvements in the living of rural women due to different initiatives taken by the cooperative societies. A study focusing on the cooperative society saving scheme in rural Nigeria showed that members of the study were satisfied with a program that provided money saving (Oluyombo & Business, 2013). Members developed self-esteem as "part owners" of the program as a result of the mandatory savings in which they participate, and they do not want the program to fail. The program not only provided better ways of finance improvement but also improved the self-esteem among the rural participants majority of which were women (62.5%). In a thrive to replicate the efforts of cooperative societies on a national scale, the Nigerian federal government start the National Social Investment Program (NSIP) (James, Ayobami, & Adeagbo, 2019). The government's enterprise empowerment initiative programme initiated under NSIP provided market women, artists, and dealers with access to loans and financing, who would not otherwise prioritized a bank (Idowu, 2019). An analysis of the effect of NSIP on the employment status of the rural and urban regions of Gombe state of Nigeria showed that NSIP have the potential of reducing the high rates of unemployment among the youth of Nigeria. 47% of the study respondents were female and 63% respondents agreed that NSIP helped them empower which ultimately affected the poverty status (Sani, Salisu, & Tijjani, 2020). This above discussion about the role of SE in Africa made it clear that different measures

are taken in different regions of Africa to ensure financial as well as social growth which are important in attaining sustainable development goals.

ROLE OF SOLIDARITY ECONOMY IN TUNISIAN CONTEXT

Following weeks of popular uprising and anti-government protests, President Zine El Abidine Ben Ali's regime crumbled on January 14, 2011. Tunisians had finally dared to do the unthinkable after more than two decades of quiet and terror. This revolutionary movement is known as the Jasmin revolution which promoted drastic changes in Tunisia (Arieff, 2012). Tunisia's democratic transition began that year, following a wave of popular movements that highlighted major socioeconomic issues such as regional inequality and high unemployment rates, particularly among young people and women in rural areas. Since then, the SE movement particularly supported by social entrepreneurship, has grown in response to different public and private initiatives, which began informally with unstructured acts before to 2011. Prior to 2011, informal activities were conducted, mostly through semi-state institutions and a microfinance system, according to the Employment Non-Discrimination Act (ENDA) (Fridhi, 2021). SE presented as a replacement for the public sector, as a means of creating jobs and addressing social and economic issues. In a similar vein, tourism was the first sector to initiate new socially beneficial projects. These new ventures aimed to create jobs while also promoting local tourism in order to reduce reliance on international tourism. The figure of the rural Tunisian woman became more evident in this environment and under the empowerment narrative (Benali & Belhaouane, 2019). Further, Tunisian government's development plan 2016-20 prioritized SE on a national scale which made to further experimentation of this approach in Tunisia (ANDP, 2016). This plan discussed in a separate part that "SSE will be given a prominent place in the wealth production and distribution system, social services, and environmental protection". The Workers' Union (UGTT) initiated a draft organic law on the SSE in 2017. In 2018, this project was presented to the administration and the parliament. However, it took a long time to debate and was finally approved on June 30, 2020. Law No. 2020-30 of Tunisia is based on the Social and Solidarity Economy (ILO, 2020A). This delay inhibits Tunisia from moving forward and promoting the development of the SSE. The new law governs and legitimizes Tunisia's SSE sector. It entails the establishment of a public structure dedicated to the SSE, dubbed the "Tunisian Social and Solidarity Economy Authority." This law establishes the first regulatory framework for the sector in order to expand its contribution to job creation and economic growth. It gives the SSE entities legitimacy, allowing them to receive proper funding (Mouelhi et al., 2021).

Several projects had been initiated in the recent past for the promotion of solidarity economy in Tunisia. Promotion of organizations and mechanisms of social and solidarity economy (PROMESS) Tunisia is one among few projects which made a successful image among Tunisians. This project stayed in action from June 2016 to September 2020 with an to promote organizations and mechanisms of the social and solidarity economy in order to create long-term and decent jobs for young women and men in Tunisia (ILO, 2020B). Based on the reports of the project, it provided 300 direct and 3000 indirect jobs to Tunisian population 60% of which were women. More than 1Million people were affected with the project's key theme of

SSE. Further, this project helped building and consolidation of 32 SSE enterprises and organizations (figure 1) which are currently promoting the message of SSE throughout the northwest region of Tunisia (ILO, 2020C). In addition to this, the project helped in the development of legal and institutional framework for SSE, developed tools for sustainable SSE and strengthened the already present SE institutes.

Figure 1: Organizations and companies created with PROMESS (ILO, 2020C)

IESS-Kairouan project is another example of SE which responds to the fulfillment of five years national plan for promoting SE in Tunisia. This project started in 2019 and is expected to be implemented till 2027. The IESS-Kairouan project is completely in line with the COSOP 2019-2024 goal of improving the living conditions, incomes, and resilience of the rural poor, particularly women and young people. It addresses multiple Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), including no poverty, zero hunger, gender equality, and climate change action (IFAD, 2020). Some other SE projects which are ongoing in Tunisia includes JEUN'ESS, Lab'ess and SDPI. JEUN'ESS aims to produce respectable opportunities for young people in underprivileged communities, and aid in the transition to the formal economy by promoting the SSE (ILO, 2019).

Lab'ess aspires to actively contribute to the sustainable growth of players in social innovation in order to successfully respond to the country's socioeconomic demands (DARPE, 2021). The SDPI project seeks to review and develop methodology and indicator systems for measuring

and evaluating the performance of private sector enterprises and SSE organizations in respect to the 2030 Agenda's vision and goals (UNRISD, 2018). Above discussion made it clear that SE has travelled a long way in Tunisia from its start back in 2011. A gradual change was observed through time in the business policies and institutional reforms of Tunisia with the introduction of SE which was ultimately accepted in 2020 with the inclusion of SE based law in Tunisian constitution. This change had a greater effect on young and marginalized rural Tunisians most of which were women.

CONCLUSION

Solidarity economy provided an alternate solution to the underlying conditions caused by the crisis of 2008. Several countries adopted this plan of action with different movements for ensuring social justice alongside making a stable approach towards economy. France and South American movements made these countries the pioneers of SE which set an example for other countries to follow. The developing world adopted this term with variant names based on the conditions of crisis in each country.

Dispute of rights and inferiority of workers in several sectors of the world provided SE as an alternate solution to the global liberalization. All the developed countries, the countries in African continent and Tunisia considered the need of SE from its inception which legalized and was supported by the state laws with the onset of time. The conference of Africa and the Jasmin revolution in Tunisia started the concept of SE in respective continents and countries which led to the development of several frameworks.

These frameworks were recognized as unformal in the beginning but with the passage of time, state of each respective country recognized its importance and provided legal support by addressing laws based on SE as well as including SE in the national development plans. Providence of a legal framework to the SE made is possible to develop different initiatives in the form of projects and institutes with the main focus to endorse the ideology of solidarity within local business setups. Such actions targeted the young and marginalized population which mostly involved women belonging from backward rural areas. Though SE is promoting a great deal of positive vibes among the rural women due to the providence of opportunities, equality and solidarity which help them to earn a better living, still, there is a long way to go. All of the projects and policies are in the initial phases of implementation which require efficient follow ups and evaluations the strengthen the roots of SE and provide better alternatives if need be.

REFERENCES

- Allard, J., & Davidson, C. (2008). *Solidarity economy: building alternatives for people and planet*: Lulu. com.
- Ali, S. (2009). Impact of the financial crisis on Africa. <https://carnegieendowment.org/2009/04/15/impact-of-financial-crisis-on-africa-pub-22995#:~:text=The%20global%20financial%20crisis%20is,in%20export%20prices%20and%20volumes.&text=During%20the%20second%20half%20of,between%20July%20and%20December%202008.>
- ANDP. (2016). <https://andp.unescwa.org/plans/1257>

- Arief, A. (2012). *Political Transition in Tunisia and Egypt: Unrest and Revolution*, edited by De Leon, JC and Jones, CR, 1-43. New York: Nova Science.
- Baron, C. (2007). Transfert du concept d'économie solidaire en Afrique francophone: paradoxes et atouts. *Revue Tiers Monde*(2), 325-342.
- Benali, A., & Belhaouane, A. (2019). Questioning the Empowerment Discourse: The Case of Rural Women in Ecotourism in Post-revolutionary Tunisia. In *Critical Tourism Studies Proceedings: CTS 2019* (pp. 81): Thompson Rivers University.
- Björkman Nyqvist, M., Guariso, A., Svensson, J., & Yanagizawa-Drott, D. (2019). Reducing child mortality in the last mile: experimental evidence on community health promoters in Uganda. *American Economic Journal: Applied Economics*, 11(3), 155-192.
- Boas, T. C., & Gans-Morse, J. (2009). Neoliberalism: From new liberal philosophy to anti-liberal slogan. *Studies in Comparative International Development*, 44(2), 137-161.
- Bresser-Pereira, L. C. (2010). The global financial crisis and a new capitalism? *Journal of Post Keynesian Economics*, 32(4), 499-534.
- Calderón-Milán, M.-J., Calderón-Milán, B., & Barba-Sánchez, V. (2020). Labour Inclusion of People with Disabilities: What Role Do the Social and Solidarity Economy Entities Play? *Sustainability*, 12(3), 1079.
- Dash, A., & Morais, L. (2015). Mapping the SSE Landscape in India and Brazil through South-South and triangular cooperation: a focus on Gender-Based Initiatives in Social and Solidarity economy. Research Coordinated by: Anita Amorim: Emerging Special Partnerships Unit, PARDEV ILO, Geneva.
- DARPE. (2021). Available at: <https://darpe.me/implement-entries/the-social-and-solidarity-economy-laboratory-labess/>
- Department of Social Welfare. (2021). Available at: <http://www.npo.gov.za/>
- Dubois, L. (2021). The impact of solidarity economy on poverty: The case of public centres of solidarity economy in Bahia, Brazil. *World Development Perspectives*, 23, 100343.
- El Hidhri, D. (2017). L 'Economie Sociale et Solidaire: Un Levier pour une Révolution Economique. C· A· Perspectives on Tunisia(03-2017).
- Fonteneau, B., Neamtan, N., Wanyama, F., Morais, L., Poorter, M. d., Borzaga, C., . . . Ojong, N. (2011). Social and solidarity economy: our common road towards decent work.
- Fraisse, L., Gardin, L., Laville, J.-L., Petrella, F., & Richez-Battesti, N. (2016). Social enterprise in France: at the crossroads of the social economy, solidarity economy and social entrepreneurship?
- Fridhi, B. (2021). Social entrepreneurship and social enterprise phenomenon: toward a collective approach to social innovation in Tunisia. *Journal of Innovation Entrepreneurship*, 10(1), 1-21.
- HAAS, E. (2012). The News Media and the Conservative Heritage Foundation: Promoting Education Advocacy at the Expense of Authority. In *Global neoliberalism and education and its consequences* (pp. 191-227): Routledge.
- Haddar, M., El Hidhri, D., and Bel Haj Rhouma, A. (2017). Etude Stratégique sur l'Economie Sociale et Solidaire en Tunisie. PNUD report. (http://www.socioeco.org/bdf_fiche-document-5673_fr.html)
- Holland, D., Nonini, D. M., Lutz, C., Bartlett, L., Frederick-McGlathery, M., Guldbrandsen, T. C., & Murillo, E. G. (2007). *Local democracy under siege: Activism, public interests, and private politics*: NYU Press.
- Idowu, H. A. (2019). An Appraisal of the Role of Social and Solidarity Economy in Achieving Sustainable Finance in Nigeria.

IFAD. (2020). Available at: <https://www.ifad.org/en/-/document/tunisia-2000002075-iess-kairouan-project-design-report>

International labor organization. (2020) A. Available at: https://www.ilo.org/global/topics/cooperatives/news/WCMS_749015/lang--en/index.htm

International labor organization. (2020) B. Available at: https://www.ilo.org/global/topics/cooperatives/projects/WCMS_532871/lang--en/index.htm

International labor organization. (2020) C. Available at: https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---ed_emp/--emp_ent/---coop/documents/generic_document/wcms_747334.pdf

International labor organization. (2019). Available at: https://www.ilo.org/global/topics/cooperatives/projects/WCMS_744336/lang--en/index.htm

International labor organization. (2009). Available at: <http://www.ilo.org/ilc/ILCSessions/previous-sessions/98thSession/lang--en/index.htm>

James, A. T., Ayobami, A. O., & Adeagbo, A. J. C. J. o. E. (2019). Raising Employability Bar and Building Entrepreneurial Capacity in Youth: A Case Study of National Social Investment Programme in Nigeria. 3(2).

Korea Labor Institute, Korea Social Enterprise Promotion Agency. (2018). 2017 social economy performance analysis (in Korean). Seoul: Ministry of Employment and Labor and Korea Social Enterprise Promotion Agency.

Laville, J.-L. (2010). The solidarity economy: an international movement. *RCCS Annual Review. A selection from the Portuguese journal Revista Crítica de Ciências Sociais*(2).

Laville, J.-L. (2015). Social and solidarity economy in historical perspective. *Social Solidarity Economy: Beyond the Fringe*, 41-56.

Lee, R., Leyshon, A., Aldridge, T., Tooke, J., Williams, C., & Thrift, N. (2004). Making geographies and histories? Constructing local circuits of value. *Environment Planning D: Society Space*, 22(4), 595-617.

Leyshon, A., Lee, R., & Williams, C. C. (2003). *Alternative economic spaces*: Sage.

Mayo, E., & Boyle, D. (1999). Let a thousand monies bloom. *Local Economy*, 14(4), 290-294.

Mouelhi, R. B. A., Braham, M. B., & Ghazali, M. (2021). The Social and Solidarity Economy in Tunisia and its role in formalising the Informal Economy: a qualitative survey.

Museum, S. D. (2020). Humanizing scholarly resistance: Toward greater solidarity in social justice advocacy within the neoliberal academy. *International Journal of Qualitative Studies in Education*, 33(2), 140-150.

Nardi, J. (2016). Solidarity economy in Europe: An emerging movement with a common vision. *European Summer School Prague, Czech Republic*.

Navarro, V. (2007). Neoliberalism as a class ideology; or, the political causes of the growth of inequalities. *International Journal of Health Services*, 37(1), 47-62.

Nelson, S. C., & Katzenstein, P. J. (2014). Uncertainty, risk, and the financial crisis of 2008. *International Organization*, 68(2), 361-392.

North, P. (2007). Money and liberation: The micropolitics of alternative currency movements: JSTOR.

Oluoyombo, P. J. E. R. J. o. E., & Business. (2013). Impact of cooperative societies savings scheme in Rural finance: Some evidence from Nigeria. 11(1).

Poirier, Y. (2014). Social Solidarity Economy and Related Concepts, Origins and Definitions: An International Perspective.

Sani, I. M., Salisu, I. M., & Tijjani, Z. J. J. o. G. S. S. (2020). National Social Investment Programme: A Panacea to Unemployment in Nigeria. 1(4), 111-122.

Schaaf, M., Fox, J., Topp, S. M., Warthin, C., Freedman, L. P., Robinson, R. S., . . . Zanchetta, M. J. I. j. f. e. i. h. (2018). Community health workers and accountability: reflections from an international “think-in”. 17(1), 1-5.

Simpson, D., Lumsden, E., & McDowall Clark, R. (2015). Neoliberalism, global poverty policy and early childhood education and care: A critique of local uptake in England. *Early Years*, 35(1), 96-109.

Steinman, S. (2010). An exploratory study into factors influencing an enabling environment for social enterprises in South Africa: Citeseer.

Steinman, S. J. I. T. C., ILO. Retrieved December. (2017). Public policies for the social and solidarity economy: Towards an enabling environment. The case of South Africa. 29, 2020.

UNRISD. (2018). Sustainable Development Performance Indicators. Available at: [https://www.unrisd.org/unrisd/website/projects.nsf/\(httpProjects\)/B2A0A8A40BE9308CC12583350053ACDF?OpenDocument&category=Case+Studies](https://www.unrisd.org/unrisd/website/projects.nsf/(httpProjects)/B2A0A8A40BE9308CC12583350053ACDF?OpenDocument&category=Case+Studies)

Watson, K. (2019). Financial Management in Non-Profit Organizations.

World Bank. (2019). https://www.theglobaleconomy.com/South-Korea/Female_labor_force_participation/